

Lymphangiomatous Tonsillar polyp

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Introduction

Benign tumors or tumor-like lesions of the palatine tonsil are less common than malignancies. Squamous papillomas account for the majority of the benign lesions, whereas vascular tumors are reportedly rare. Because of the unusual clinical and pathologic features of these polyps, pathologists and clinicians alike may have difficulty in classifying them correctly¹. Therefore, we describe the clinical and histopathologic features. They are benign lymph-vascular proliferations with varying degrees of fibrous, adipose, and lymphoid components. Tonsillar lymphangiomatous polyp is a kind of hamartomatous lesion and it has been described by different nomenclatures such as lymphangiectatic fibrous polyp, polypoid lymphangioma of the tonsil, hamartomatous tonsillar polyp and so on². It is lined by squamous epithelia and its stroma is composed of variably loose or more dense collagenous tissue and adipose tissue, and this usually contains dilated lymphatic channels and various components of lymphoid tissue³. It is a rare polypoid mass that generally arises from a pedicle attached to the tonsil and projecting into the oropharynx². Although this is a rare clinical and pathologic entity for pathologists and clinicians, the diagnosis is not so difficult if one has a bit of theoretical knowledge of this entity.

Case report

A 22 year old lady came to VSGH with the chief complaint of a mass in left tonsillar region since 5 years. Patient was relatively asymptomatic before 5 years when she noticed a small swelling in left tonsillar region which gradually and painlessly increased upto its present size. On Inspection, a 3×1.5×1 cm pedunculated mass was present in left tonsillar region, which moved on swallowing. On palpation, our inspectory findings were confirmed. Mass was non warm, non tender, soft to firm in consistency, mobile and has peduncle attached to left tonsillar fossa. All the routine blood investigations and chest X-ray were normal. The mass with its peduncle was cauterised with bipolar cautery under general anaesthesia and sent for histopathological examination which reported the mass as tonsillar lymphangiomatous

polyp. There was no bleed during surgery suggesting lymphangiomatous nature. There was no recurrence after one year of follow-up of the patient.

Fig-1 Pedunculated polyp from left palatine tonsil.

Fig-2 Post operative cut specimen

Fig-3 three components of tonsillar lymphangiomatous polyps: dilated lymphatic channels, fibrous stroma, and lymphoid tissue.

Discussion

The head and neck are the most common anatomic regions for lymphangiomatous lesions, accounting for over 90% of all lymphangiomas⁴. Most arise in the skin and subcutaneous tissues, but other sites include the larynx, parotid gland, mouth, and tongue⁵. The tonsil is a less common site for the development of lymphangiomatous tumors, and their classification in this location is confusing. In the early part of the 20th century, histologically identical lesions of the tonsil were reported by a number of different names, including angiomas⁶, angiofibromas, or fibroangiomas⁷. Still others have had difficulty classifying their cases specifically, and have named them fibrolipomas after the stromal components, or have given them a more descriptive diagnosis, such as “polypoid tumor containing fibroadipose tissue”⁸. Consequently, the true incidence of

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these lesions is difficult to accurately assess from the literature. As such, lymphangiomas tonsillar tumors have a higher incidence than is reported. Furthermore, they are probably more common than other angiomatous lesions in this location. As noted in the literature⁹, the lymphatic channels of LAPs are frequently dilated, but generally are not as prominent as in the typical lymphangioma. In addition, the stromal components are frequently more abundant than the vessels. We agree with the assertion that these lesions are most likely hamartomatous because they consist of a haphazard proliferation of elements that are normally found in the tonsil. These tumors occasionally become large and cause obstructive symptoms and in these circumstances, have generally been present for years, up to 30 years in one reported case¹⁰. Benign tumors or tumor-like lesions of the palatine tonsil are less common than malignant ones. Squamous papilloma accounts for the majority of the benign lesions, whereas vascular tumors are rarely reported. The tonsil is a less common site for the development of lymphangiomas lesions. Kardon *et al.*⁶ reviewed 26 cases of lymphangiomas polyps and they described the various histologic features of the polyps. They were usually covered by squamous epithelium and showed a variable degree of epithelial hyperplasia and proliferation of lympho-vascular channels. Collagen, adipose tissue and lymphocytic infiltration were present in the stroma. The differential diagnoses should include juvenile angiofibroma, papilloma, and lymphangioma. It is important to distinguish lymphangiomas polyps from juvenile angiofibroma, since the latter lesion should usually be treated more aggressively to prevent possible recurrence. Clinically, angiofibromas typically occur in the nasopharynx of adolescent males, often as large tumors with extensive growth and even bone erosion and present with epistaxis due to the rich blood supply. Histologically, the stroma of angiofibromas is more cellular, composed of stellate and plump cells, and contains branching thin walled vascular channels. On the other hand, lymphangiomas polyps usually have a relatively paucicellular fibrous background and more lymphocytes, and squamous papilloma is usually an exophytic surface epithelial proliferation that is arranged in multiple layers lacking lymphatic and lymphocytic components.

Summary

Lymphangiomas polyps of the tonsil are benign tumors that most frequently present as mass lesions and are composed of dilated lymphatic channels amid a

fibrous, lymphoid, and/or adipose stroma. They are most likely hamartomatous proliferations, and as such are cured by simple surgical excision. After surgical resection, there were no incidences of recurrence. They (LAPs) have a varied histology and may exhibit papillary growth and are probably not as rare as reported in the literature.

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